

IN THE NAME OF GODMENT

(Identity impression)

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Review:

Pragmatism is a philosophy that first appeared in the United States and had a great impact on the thinking and intellectual life of this land. This philosophy emerged in the late nineteenth century with thinkers such as William James and John Dewey. According to these thinkers, pragmatism is a revolution against idealism and pure intellectual exploration that is of no use to man. While this philosophy is a way of solving intellectual problems that can be very useful in human progress. The word pragmatism is derived from the Greek word (pragma) and means action. The term was first used by Charles Sanders Pierce, an American logician. He meant to use the word as a way to solve and evaluate intellectual problems. But gradually the meaning of pragmatism changed. In some studies, pragmatism is considered as one of the competing paradigms with the interpretive paradigm, and thus these views question the dualism of positivism and anti-positivism.

Keywords: Pragmatism, Pragmatism, Positivism, William James, Charles Sanders

Introduction:

From the point of view of pragmatism, all our ideas, concepts, judgments, and opinions are rules for our "behavior" (pragma), but their "truth" lies only in their practical utility for our lives. From the point of view of pragmatism, the criterion of truth is usefulness, benefit, result, and not conformity to objective reality. In fact, the truth of everything is proved by its end result. Pragmatism is a method in philosophy that,

while acknowledging the impossibility of proving certain things, accepts them with regard to their application in human life. Proponents of her case have been working to make the actual transcript of this statement available online. Opposition groups call the group moderate (or conservative). "Pragmatist" statesmen and politicians are those who put the practical possibilities and expediency of the day before their own, in other words, show flexibility to advance their goals or stay in power. Among the Western schools of the twentieth century, we can mention three important philosophical and ideological schools of Darwinism, pragmatism and American humanism, which played a major role in the development of Western culture. The leaders of these schools benefited from Darwin's school of evolution. The rise of Darwinism prompted Western religious intellectuals, especially William James and John Dewey, to take a stand against the teachings of the church as well as human nature. "Pragmatist" statesmen and politicians are those who put the practical possibilities and expediency of the day before their own, in other words, show flexibility to advance their goals or stay in power. Among the Western schools of the twentieth century, we can mention three important philosophical and ideological schools of Darwinism, pragmatism and American humanism, which played a major role in the development of Western culture. The leaders of these schools benefited from Darwin's school of evolution. The rise of Darwinism prompted Western religious intellectuals, especially William James and John Dewey, to take a stand against the teachings of the church as well as human nature. Thus, Darwin's theory was the basis for the emergence of

the school of pragmatism and humanism and other intellectual-philosophical developments in the West, the effects of which appeared in the vital structure of Western civil society. In the following, we will discuss the general principles of this school ...

Pragmatism:

History

Pragmatism is a philosophy that first emerged in the United States and had a great impact on the thinking and intellectual life of this land. This philosophy emerged in the late nineteenth century with thinkers such as Charles Sanders Peirce, William James, and later John Dewey. In fact, although it was William James who first used the term in philosophical texts, William James himself credits Charles Sanders with the use of the term. It is well known that Charles Sanders Peirce uses the term in his discussions at the Metaphysical Club. The Metaphysical Club was a philosophical association founded by Oliver Wendell Holmes, William James, and Charles Sanders Peirce in 1872 in Cambridge, Massachusetts. Charles Sanders Peirce uses the term in discussions at the club, but it was William James who introduced it into philosophical texts. In his book *Pragmatism*, William James writes:

The term ["pragmatism"] is derived from the Greek word [thing] meaning action; The words "action" and "action" in our language also come from it. Charles Sanders Peirce introduced it to philosophy in 1878. In an article entitled "How to Clarify Our Ideas," Mr. Peirce said in January of that year, after pointing out that our beliefs are in fact rules for action, to expand the meaning of an idea / belief. , We just have to

determine what behavior that thought of belief causes: In our view, that behavior is the only meaning of that belief / thought; And the obvious truth behind our intellectual distinctions, however subtle, is that only those are used that contain a possible difference in action; Therefore, if we want to achieve a clear picture of an object / object in our thoughts, we simply have to consider what imaginable effects that object / object originates on the action, what effects on the senses we should expect from it, and for what reactions. We have to prepare ourselves. So our perception of these effects, whether direct or intermittent, is in our view of that object;

; If that idea has a positive meaning at all. This is the principle of the press, the principle of pragmatism. This principle was ignored by almost everyone for almost twenty years, until I reiterated it in a lecture at the Professor Howison Philosophical Society at the University of California. Of course, it must be said that later there were disagreements between Charles Sanders Press and William James over the implications of this philosophical current. Clearly, Charles Sanders Press did not quite agree with William James' interpretations of pragmatism. This disagreement can be attributed in part to the rational orientations of Charles Sanders Press and the psychological inclinations of William James.

This controversy extends to the present, with some contemporary pragmatists claiming to be followers of Charles Sanders Press and some claiming to be followers of William James.

According to these thinkers, pragmatism is a revolution against idealism and pure intellectual exploration that is of no use to man, while the

philosophy of pragmatism is a method of solving intellectual problems that can be very useful in human progress. The American philosopher Richard Rorty belonged to the philosophical tradition of American pragmatism; But this philosophy became more popular in England and is known to have become the philosophical basis of English education. For example, religion is not debatable from the point of view of modern philosophy because it is not scientific, but pragmatism considers it due to its application, which also has benefits for human beings.

The meaning of pragmatism in a certain culture

((.)) [فر] (پ Practical philosophy, originality of action, pragmatism.

The meaning of pragmatism in Amid Persian culture

Philosophical thinking based on the fact that the truth of any proposition must be recognized by adapting it to the practical results and benefits derived from it, the originality of action.

Pragmatism in the Islamic Encyclopedia

The word "Pragmatism" means pragmatism derived from "Pragma" meaning action or action, and pragmatism or the school of originality of action as opposed to "Intellectualism" or the school of thought and opinion, is a philosophical view that always focuses on action, action and what It works, it emphasizes.

Pragmatism was born in the United States in the last third of the nineteenth century and influenced a variety of sciences, including

psychology and education. This school of philosophy with the characteristics of American life was first introduced as a method by Charles Pierce in 1878. Then there are William James, John Dewey and Arthur Balfour, Ferdinand Schiller and Hans Weinger. They presented several narrations about it. The term was used by Kant, not as a method or a school, but as rules based on experience in the field of practical ethics. Attention to the end of the verb, in such rules, led Kant to call them pragmatic. Reaction against rationalism

Emile Durkheim saw pragmatism as a reaction to traditional rationalism; Dewey and Herbert Mead, like Marx, argue that traditional philosophy is meaningless, formal, and useless. According to Kaplan, pragmatism is a replica of semantic empiricism, which is itself the result of the development of epistemic empiricism. Pragmatism is a view, method, and philosophy that uses the practical results of ideas and beliefs as a criterion for determining their value and truth. According to William James, it is a view that from the beginning of objects, abandons principles and categories and pays attention to the end of objects, achievements, results and practical facts. The school of pragmatism emphasizes experience, empirical research, and truth in terms of convincing results.

Its main emphasis is on method and perspective, so it was not initially considered a coherent and systematic system; In this sense, Dewey uses the term "Instrumentalism" instead of pragmatism, because it places more emphasis on the methodological aspect. Interprets an organism's

adaptation to the environment; therefore, according to Dewey, pragmatism is an experimental research method.

Philosophy of Pragmatism

The word pragmatism is derived from the Greek word (pragma) and means action. The term was first used by Charles Sanders Pierce, an American logician. He meant to use the term as a way to solve and evaluate intellectual problems. But gradually the meaning of pragmatism changed.

Now, pragmatism has become a theory that says: Truth is something that is good from a human point of view. In other words, pragmatism means that any theory or doctrine should be judged on the basis of the conclusions drawn from it. According to pragmatists, if an idea leads to a good and efficient result for human beings, it should be considered real. Truth is not something that exists independently of man.

Until now, the main and common theory about truth was that truth is separate from man; Who knows it or not.

But pragmatism believed that truth was not a matter of separation from man; Rather, the only reason why an opinion is right and true and an opinion is false and wrong is that the former is useful to man in practice and is efficient and effective for him, and the latter is not. In this way, the meaning of the truth in pragmatism changed. The truth of any proposition is measured only by its practical results, not by comparison with external reality. A thought or belief, as long as it is only a belief, is in itself neither right nor wrong; Rather, it is only during the experiment

and its practical application that it becomes true or false according to the results from which it is considered.

For example, religion is not debatable from the point of view of modern philosophy because it is not scientific, but pragmatism accepts it according to its application, which also has benefits for human beings (moral, social, etc.).

According to the school of pragmatism, thoughts and ideas are like tools to solve human problems; As long as they have a beneficial effect, they are true and true, and then they become false and erroneous. In this way, an idea may be used and effective for a while, and therefore it is true at the moment; But later the results may not be satisfactory and then, it turns into a false theory.

Therefore, truth is not static and immutable; Rather, it evolves and evolves over time. What is true now may not be true in the future;

Because in the future, other thoughts and ideas will become real and common according to new conditions and situations. All things are subject to results, and therefore right is relative; That is, it depends on a certain time, place and stage of science and history. We will never reach the absolute truth. Because our science, our problems and our problems are always changing, and at each stage, the truth will be what enables us to satisfactorily examine and solve the current problems and issues of that time.

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that any theory or doctrine should be judged on the basis of the results obtained from it.

According to pragmatists, if an idea leads to a good and useful result for human beings, it should be considered real. Truth is not something that exists independently of man. Until now, the main and common theory about truth was that truth is something separate from man; who knows it or not. For example, the rotation of the earth around the sun is something that has always been true; However, for thousands of years it was thought that the earth was fixed and the sun revolved around it. Accordingly, the truth and correctness of any theory was its correspondence with reality and its incorrectness was its incompatibility with reality. But pragmatism believed that truth was not a matter of separation from man;

Rather, the only reason why one opinion is right and one opinion, and one opinion is false and wrong, is that the former is useful to man in practice and is efficient and effective for him, and the latter is not. In this way, the meaning of the truth in pragmatism changed. The truth of any statement is measured only by its practical results, not by comparison with external reality. A thought or belief, as long as it is only a belief, is in itself neither right nor wrong; Rather, it is only during the experiment and its practical application that it becomes true or false according to the results from which it is considered. Thus, for example, before the discovery of the United States, for example, the idea that there was a land between Europe and Asia was neither true nor false; But after the discovery of the United States, this idea came true. (While, according to popular belief, this idea was correct even before the discovery of the United States. And human

problems, as long as they have a beneficial effect, are right and true, and then they go wrong, so an idea may work for a while and be effective, and therefore it is real now, but it may be later. It does not have satisfactory results, and then it becomes a false theory, so the truth is not static, it evolves over time. Is not true in the future;

Because in the future, other thoughts and ideas will become real and common according to new conditions and situations. All things are subject to results, and therefore right is relative; That is, it depends on a certain time, place and stage of science and history. We will never reach the absolute truth. Because our science, our problems and our problems are always changing and at every stage, the truth will be what enables us to satisfactorily examine and solve the current problems and issues of that time.

Pragmatism as a philosophy of the public

Since we consider James to be the initiator of pragmatism, I will focus on aspects of the pragmatic approach that James emphasizes. In my view, the fact that James's book *Pragmatism* matured by giving lectures to a wide audience, most of whom were not philosophers, shows that pragmatism is more than just a kind of academic philosophy. It is important, then, that both James and Dewey and the late Richard Rorty and Cornell West were philosophers who addressed issues of public concern about language and were fully available to the public. In fact, Dewey writes:

"Philosophy rediscovers itself when it can no longer be a tool for dealing with the problems of philosophers, in a way that philosophers

can use it to deal with the problems of human beings." I believe that Dewey believed that philosophy should avoid delving into the scholastic issues it has created. By taking a factor perspective, philosophy can be "avoided" in this way, a term I borrow from West.

When philosophers apply philosophical thought to areas of human activity other than philosophy itself, philosophy deals directly with human problems. Dewey's book *Democracy and Education* (1916) is a prime example of this.

In fact, I recognize the influence of pragmatism on various cases of mixed philosophies, even in cases where this effect has not been acknowledged. But I am very pleased to see explicit references to pragmatism, for example in the works of Elizabeth Anderson and Larry Hickman.

Pragmatism as optimism

When James reads Morrison Swift's descriptions of the sufferings of poverty in his first speech, it must have seemed to the audience that he was crossing a line, the line between philosophy and journalism, or perhaps between philosophy and sociology.

Of course, it is wrong to claim that James in these speeches sought to provide a solution to poverty or that he formed a philosophy about poverty or journalism. He reads Swift's descriptions to make his audience aware of the facts that have caught his eye, and he believes that things are worth pondering. He saw the need for a philosophy that combined "scientific fidelity to facts and attention to them, as well as confidence in human values." "I see pragmatism as a philosophy that can meet both

needs," he says. "This philosophy can remain religious, like rationalist views, and at the same time maintain a deep closeness to reality, like empiricist views." Facts that were specifically related to pragmatism were facts about poverty and other evils. James also considered absolute idealism, as well as any religion that presupposes the God of the omnipotent and omnipotent universe, and tries to deny the reality of evil, unacceptable. The solution that James ultimately proposes in his final speech is not a requirement of pragmatism, but he emphasizes that "my pragmatism is not flawed" and calls it "optimism." This view is composed of the following three statements:

1. The world is imperfect, or evil is real.
2. The future is not determined; Humans can work together to make the world a better place.
3. In this endeavor, a finite divinity helps human beings.

In what follows, I examine Propositions 1 and 2 to formulate optimism, and I also examine Proposition 3 to propose a particular theism. James's solution to the problem of evil is finite divinity. It can be said that James abandons the problem of evil reflection, that is, whether evil is real (a problem from the point of view of a passive observer) and instead raises the practical question of how evil can be overcome (a problem from the point of view of the active factor).

In fact, Propositions 2 and 3 are metaphysical hypotheses, and I will talk more about James' approach to these hypotheses.

Although we are opportunistic, we do not have to accept relativism. We can become aware of our situation and thus change our perception of our

environment. If so, that is, if we accept the inevitability of multiple perspectives, we will be a pluralist in the same sense as James.

Improvement, with or without Proposition 3, is a view that has never been needed as it is now. James compares optimism - which he describes as "saving the world is possible" - to two perspectives:

It is impossible to save the world, or it is absolutely certain. I'm not sure exactly what James means by "salvation," but we can defensively mean that controlling global warming before it destroys human life or civilization. It is salvation. Achieving salvation in this sense requires the effort of human beings individually as well as nationally and internationally, and, as James points out, individual effort must be motivated by ensuring that others will make the same effort.

I do not want to say that recovery has only a global aspect. There are more limited issues that require collaborations based on the belief that things can be improved, and that requires the participation of others.

There is extensive literature on issues such as coordination and trust. This literature may be considered an example of what was previously considered a public issue and may lead to academic issues that benefit from the results of academic research. The collaboration that is required for recovery requires some kind of interdisciplinary inquiry, both in the philosophy of biomedical ethics and in the philosophy of law. In my view, these areas, which transcend traditional interdisciplinary boundaries, will flourish in the future, as they have two prerequisites for successful collaboration: exchanging perspectives rather than disregard, and the other, finding a way to reveal common or conflicting values in

order to resolve Value-oriented dilemmas. I will talk more about this later.

Pragmatism as a way to resolve metaphysical conflicts

According to James, pragmatism is a kind of philosophy, a way of resolving philosophical disputes. But pragmatism is not a philosophical "system," but an approach, a way of life, and especially a way of dealing with things. We have already seen how James deals with the problem of evil. At the same time, James proposes a way of resolving philosophical disputes: applying the pragmatic principle. I do not intend to discuss the various formulations that have been proposed from the pragmatic principle. I also do not intend to discuss the various applications for which this principle has been applied. I do not believe that the pragmatic principle, at least as James envisions it, is one aspect of pragmatism that has survived or needs to be revived. But James's initial formulation of this principle is an example of the factor perspective used on metaphysical disagreements. James writes: "To understand the meaning of an idea, we only need to determine what behavior that thought causes. "This behavior is the whole meaning of that thought." I do not intend to criticize James's account of the pragmatic principle. I just want to point out that James' emphasis on behavior naturally stems from his factor perspective.

If it is necessary to consider the difference between the two in creating particular behaviors when choosing between competing metaphysical hypotheses, then choosing one of these perspectives would be a moral choice. James, for example, believed that belief in a particular world would lead to widespread pessimism or a kind of subjectivism that would

inevitably lead to "a kind of borderless sentimentality." James' opposition to such an end leads him to an indefinite view and, consequently, to his second proposition of optimism. Maybe James is right, maybe what typically seem to be metaphysical questions are actually moral questions. But now, at the beginning of the twenty-first century, moral differences are at least as widespread as metaphysical differences. If our goal is to reach a consensus, I do not think it is a promising strategy to reduce metaphysical differences to moral differences. For example, consider the question of whether the fetus is a human or not. It is clear that the answer to this question has the effect of authorizing or forbidding certain behaviors, but because there is disagreement on this moral question - and indeed this disagreement has been much debated precisely because it is a moral disagreement.

James's method is useless to apply the pragmatic principle. One might say, however, that his question as to what behavior is appropriate to a claim or its product has the advantage of explaining why such ardent thinkers argue about the metaphysical dignity of the fetus.

Pragmatism as an approach

The Pragmatic Principle Aside from the Idea of Resolving Metaphysical Controversy As well, let us take a look at James's description of the pragmatic approach: Late. " I must say frankly that I find James' view on this quite vague.

Certainly in any research, certain things, principles and necessities are assumed by default. Certainly we can not think without thinking of all kinds of things (categories), and there is certainly nothing wrong with

searching for causes (initial things). What James wants to say is that pragmatists are not dogmatic. What is taken in a default query can be queried in another query. Pragmatists As pragmatists, they are not looking for absolutely primitive objects. In this respect, they agree with biologists who study the evolution of species, but do not think that what they are discovering is evidence for or against the intelligent design of the universe.

But as we have seen, pragmatism does not forbid people from religious inquiries, but only emphasizes that they are not scientific, a view that many scientists, both atheists and atheists, agree on. The categories that James rejects are neither general classifications nor science categories. He questions Kant's categories and objects and objects to views that are thoughtlessly and habitually expressed. The positive aspects of a pragmatic approach, as James puts it, are in fact aspects of the approach of any scientist. I can say with confidence that these aspects are alive and well among scientists and the vast majority of people.

The flourishing of modern science is largely the result of the democratization of scientific inquiry. Prerequisites are the democratization of moral inquiry, the democratization of the collective, and the establishment of ways and institutions to hear the voices of those who have seldom been taken seriously and heard.

Given that James and I claim that this pragmatic approach will dominate philosophy, we need to ask what is the point of a philosopher adopting this approach. I think the answer to this question can be found in Dewey's observation that philosophy must deal with human problems. Philosophy

should not turn away from our problems, but should help us to distinguish them clearly. If pragmatism does this and at the same time some issues remain difficult, pragmatism may be exhausted in such cases. Some argue that optimism, which is an integral part of optimism and belief in the possibility of progress, seems too simplistic in such cases. This view does not fully convince me. For some of us graduate students in the 1950s, there was so much excitement that many analytical philosophers walked with us. In this part, I take on the tone of a biography to some extent.

I worked under Reichenbach and Carnap, and I also attended lectures by Austin and Wittgenstein's students, and at the same time I was one of the people who was perhaps most influenced by Quine's analytical essay "Two Dogmas of Empiricism." From what we have heard from some of our professors about pragmatism, seeds have emerged that after a while began to sprout. This is not an opportunity to write the history of the resurgence of pragmatism; I mean these autobiographical sentences to reveal the perspective from which I predict the continuation of pragmatism. In my view, if one can claim that post-Holocaust depression led to the suppression of pragmatism, one can also claim that the civil rights movement and, shortly thereafter, the second wave of feminism revived pragmatism; Because if one hopes for good reasons that a social movement will take shape over a long period of time, one can hope for the same reasons that one will have a constructive pragmatic approach to constructive interaction with such a movement.

Pragmatism as pluralism

Pragmatists believe that we humans are social; Not because we need others to nurture, not because we need the cooperation of other human beings in the pursuit of our lives, nor because human knowledge is so vast and intertwined that each of us must rely on experience. The creativity and testimony of many people rely on the past and the present, but because each of us's self and the image we have of ourselves is largely the product of our social environment. For example, whether a person considers himself a philosopher and at the same time a mother, or considers himself a mother who teaches philosophy, depends in part on the fact that those around him value him as a philosopher.

It also depends in part on the social status of philosophers and mothers in one's society, and again in part on one's own assessment of one's abilities as a mother and as a philosopher and how one devotes oneself to these two roles.

Human beings are so-called "situational" contemporary feminists, and what each person believes to be the result of his or her own experiences is influenced by his or her position. A believer who participates in religious ceremonies has experiences that are fundamentally different from the experiences of mere observers as well as anthropological experiences that know the meaning of religious ceremonies for believers. Thus, knowledge as well as ethics are largely social.

In fact, morality is more than social knowledge, because it deals with the relations between human beings. As James says, morality is objective, because human beings consider it in their relationships with each other, and it is transmitted to each of us in the form of customary morality;

However, as Dewey emphasizes, we can improve these morals through personal reflection.

I must point out here that although we are situational, we do not have to accept relativism. We can become aware of our situation and thus change our perception of our environment. If so, that is, if we accept the inevitability of multiple perspectives, we will be a pluralist in the same sense as James. According to pluralist or individualist philosophy, truth is much broader than the actual mind of each of us, even if it is considered the "absolute thing" that knows itself fully. The facts and values of life need people to understand them. No view is absolutely general or general. Personal and non-transferable perceptions always remain, and worse than that, those who seek these perceptions from the outside never know where they are. ... »

The practical consequence of such a philosophy is democratic respect for individuality. These phrases are so familiar that it is as if our ears do not hear them at all. Because I believe pluralism is one of the greatest contributions of pragmatism to philosophy, I want to talk a little bit about this quote, but first I have to point out that James considered himself a pluralist in various senses. As mentioned earlier, he rejected determinism and believed that multiple futures were open to us. As he explained in a chapter of the book on common sense, he believed that each of us could understand what we were experiencing in at least three ways: the way of thinking based on common sense, the scientific way, and the philosophical way.

In the various chapters of the book in question, James also points to the multiplicity of perspectives that each of us has.

This is a kind of "situationalism" more radical than what some feminists, Marxists, critical theorists in the field of law, and others who emphasize social perspectives on domination and repression based on gender, class, or race. It is no coincidence that James calls this aspect of his philosophy "pluralistic or individualistic" because he refers to the plurality of individual perspectives. He makes two points in this discussion: First, the perspectives are limited, because no one can see the whole universe, and many of us cannot even see our immediate surroundings. Second, each perspective adds something to our overall picture, and so each person deserves to be listened to.

This image contains both the facts and the values of our lives. And if we ask what behavior pluralism is commensurate with or what behavior it achieves, James answers that this behavior is respect, or at least tolerance for alien perspectives. This position means that we want to hear what others have to say, we want to create institutions that make it possible for others to speak and be heard. It is more than political democracy and even more than a commitment to the rights of individuals, freedom and equality, but, as Dewey puts it, "a way of life, both socially and individually." Dewey explains this point as follows:

Pragmatist philosophers, precisely because they are pluralistic, must transcend the boundaries of philosophical schools. Although the majority of current pragmatists are trained in the context of Anglo-American

analytic philosophy, they must sooner or later turn their attention to other currents, such as continental philosophy.

"In my view, a key point in democracy as a way of life is the need for every adult to participate in shaping the values that govern human life together; "This is necessary both from the point of view of public welfare and for the prosperity of every human being as an individual."

Understanding that each human being has something valuable and a particular role to play in shaping the values that govern their collective life is now more important than ever. We can no longer limit our attention to just our fellow countrymen or to all of us. Our compatriots belong to different religious communities and all of us have different nationalities. Pluralism means respect for the diverse views and values of our world. But what exactly does respect for foreign views entail? Should we bow to some kind of extremist relativism? The factor perspective we are discussing must be able to reject relativism.

It should be noted first that others' perceptions of things may enhance our perceptions, may increase our understanding of the situation we are in, and help us understand our common situations. On the other hand, the perceptions of others may be in stark contrast to what we think, and therefore cause us to do more research, as happens intermittently in science. In other cases, it may be clear to most of us that others are clearly wrong; Over and over again, however, what only one person believed has become an accepted scientific opinion. What is at stake in these diverse cases is the pragmatic commitment to misrepresentation, the possibility that each of our beliefs may be misunderstood.

But James is not only talking about facts, he is also promoting values. When values conflict, the problem becomes significantly more complex. Some philosophers exaggerate the simplicity of resolving scientific differences and try to push the philosophy of ethics in the same direction. But they do not take into account the severity of moral differences and the difficulty of resolving them. Pragmatists seem to be committed to a kind of moral relativism by emphasizing pluralism, because they see morality as a social thing. Or, on the other hand, they tend to subjectivism, because, in their view, the morality of individuals is shaped by their personal reflections; But this is not the case.

Here, the factor perspective manifests itself once again. We reflect our values in pursuing our goals and commitments, and then examine the results of our actions. In the philosophy of ethics, like science, we learn from our own experience as well as from the experience of others. The flourishing of modern science is largely the result of the democratization of scientific inquiry. Prerequisites are the democratization of moral inquiry, the democratization of the collective, and the establishment of ways and institutions to hear the voices of those who have seldom been taken seriously and heard. Trade unions, women's democracies, and the like are examples of people with weak voices coming together to shout their views. It should be borne in mind that members of such organizations are individuals who differ widely and significantly in other matters, and these differences must also be respected. Here, both philosophical inquiry and political action are needed. I hope pluralism and

erroneousness keep us from going astray. I believe that in a world that embraces diversity, even in its smallest social units, there is a growing need for respect and tolerance, which James advocated as pluralism.

Thus much work remains for pluralist philosophers. They can formulate the concerns of groups that need to be heard;

They can address specific issues in political philosophy or the philosophy of law, and they can also clarify the basic concepts of pluralism, such as perspective or position, respect and tolerance, the idea of trying to place oneself in the perspective of others, and the like. Finally, pragmatist philosophers, precisely because they are pluralistic, must transcend the boundaries of philosophical schools. Although the majority of current pragmatists are trained in the context of Anglo-American analytic philosophy, they must sooner or later turn their attention to other currents, such as continental philosophy. In this regard, I can mention Richard Rorty's interest in Heidegger and Hillary Putnam's interest in Levinas.

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Principles of Pragmatism

- 1- Naturalism; According to this principle, any supernatural affairs or the interference of supernatural forces or natural beings are denied and equal nature exists; On the other hand, because nature is the realm of experience, naturalism requires empiricism. Therefore, according to pragmatic philosophers, experience becomes the principle. Thus, nature is the realm of man, and because of the elimination of the supernatural world, man becomes the reference of things. At the same time, scientism, in this regard, with the help of humanism and the empirical method, expands the aspects of the world within experience.
- 2- - Instrumentation; The term is in a sense equivalent to pragmatism; But as a principle, it is accepted by all pragmatists (except Pierce). Instrumentalism means that thinking, phenomena and theories are interpreted as means for the organism to adapt to the environment. The measure of it is human authority. This principle is not a tool of pragmatism.
- 3- Utilitarianism; Therefore, the principle, the end result or profit should be considered; That is, there is no fixed truth. Accordingly, the flow of things does not proceed logically, but man first considers the result and prepares it to provide that result. If, on the whole, there is truth, it also lies in the result and the end, which, according to pragmatists, make truth, action, and result human; That is, there is no such thing as truth, but it is

an absolute assumption. With this view, there will basically be no single view, and the truth will be multiplied in all dimensions and by the number of people, and thus, pluralism will be formed. Therefore, relativism and individualism are also works of this view and are among the basic principles of pragmatism.

- Scientism; This principle is one of the basic principles of this school of thought which contains humanistic tools and means that the new scientific method should be used as the basis of philosophy; According to Schiller, philosophy deals with solving human problems that uses scientific methods to benefit humans. Proponents of pragmatism have developed scientific methods in the fields of psychology, education, and social sciences in the field of human experience. Obviously, the criterion for the correctness and use of this method depends on its applicability, satisfaction, results, efficiency and usefulness in practice, and these are all advantages of the scientific method. On this basis we conclude that these principles lead to humanism;

Therefore, this school of thought should be considered a humanist school. On the other hand, pragmatism has revived and nurtured a wide range of humanists in Western culture, especially in the United States. The worldviews and views of modern Western and American humanists, popularized under the headings of Scientific Humanism or Humanistic Naturalism, are explicitly pragmatic. Perhaps that is why pragmatists are the main proponents of modern humanism in America.

theorists

- A) Charles Sanders Peirce (1839-1914); He was the father of American pragmatism in the twentieth century, which had a limited understanding of it. Otherwise the concepts are meaningless. In this regard, metaphysical concepts have no meaning, which provides grounds for doubt in religious teachings.
- B) William James (William James: 1842-1910); James pragmatism is about discovering the truth rather than expressing concepts and proving meanings. James's philosophy is more balanced than Pierce's, but the principles and content of his philosophy also doubted the facts, so much so that in religious and spiritual matters James forged the term private religious experience and reduced religious knowledge to an individual and psychological experience. In his view, beliefs and assumptions come true when they can be relatively effective in any situation and adapt to any situation. He also emphasized relativity and attention to religious tolerance, and this lack of understanding of religion in his works is due to his psychological view of religion.
- C) John Dewey (1859-1952); After James, American pragmatism was based on Dewey's thought; He sought a more moderate view. Replaced the term "warranted assertibility" with "truth"; Beliefs, then, can be reliably affirmed when they can be useful in a variety of situations.

Inspired by Darwin, he believes that the history of Western philosophy has witnessed many scientific, ideological, and historical developments that have transformed the vital, social, cultural, and religious context of

the West. He attributed these developments to the influence of Darwin's theory.

According to him, pragmatism is a school of instrumentalism, according to which the world is what man experiences. Man is the standard of everything, including the universe, God, and truth, all of which are human achievements created by him to satisfy man's outward and inward needs.

According to him, the mind as a structure and thought process has stages such as defining cognitions in the social world, determining the main lines of possible behaviors, imagining the consequences of other ways of action, aiming at unlikely possibilities and choosing the optimal way of action. This emphasis on the thought process has greatly influenced the evolution of the theory of symbolic interaction.

D) Ferdinand Schiller (F. C. Schiller); He prefers to use the word humanism instead of pragmatism. He combines logic and psychology, in which the philosopher can supervise all the sciences that deal with the discovery of human truths. The importance of psychology from Schiller's point of view is that philosophy is the domain of man and his experiences. Thus, his conception of this school, based on human originality, reflects the humanistic nature of pragmatism.

E) Herbert Mead; He can be considered one of the leaders of pragmatism, and Dewey was the main interpreter of these theories.

Mead's two important intellectual roots in particular, and the theory of symbolic interaction in general, are the philosophy of pragmatism and psychological behaviorism.

General characteristics of pragmatism

Philosophy in this school is devoid of theoretical goals and pays more attention to practice.

In fact, pragmatism is a perverted form of the main purpose of pragmatism; That is, instead of knowing the truth, he considers some kind of action and experience as the principle and opinion as the means:

(All these pragmatists consider opinion as a function of thought as a function of action and attack rationalism.

They tend to be empirical and base their views not on pre-experience concepts but on living experience. Defines the dynamic... Nature is considered the flow of constant becoming. Natural science is important and fundamental to biology. The image that the pragmatists present of the world also seems separate from other philosophies; Because when we look at what is shown in experience instead of generalities, it leads to a cosmology separate from other philosophies.

Materialists and idealists and others present a picture of the world that always has certain characteristics. Contrary to this view, pragmatists are faced with a multifaceted world; a world with many attributes and possibilities that cannot be studied all at once. Rather, the universe must be studied experimentally as it appears and evolves, and as our course of

nature progresses, so must our understanding of it. It is a kind of degrading of philosophy and expectations for practical life to philosophize:

According to the theory of the originality of pragmatism, the purpose of our rational activities is to try to solve the problems that arise during our efforts to examine experience.

"We think only to solve our problems," says James, one of the leading philosophers of pragmatism. For example, the idea that our world is a spiritual world

(In American-British pragmatism it is not just a theory of cognition. Often a whole philosophy of life is added to it, which is very similar to Bergson's philosophy. According to it, reality is not a fixed thing but is freely creative and in flux Understanding is incapable of receiving it, every knowledge is based on experience. "We think only to solve our problems," says James, one of the leading philosophers of pragmatism. For example, the idea that our world is a spiritual world

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Anglo-American pragmatists also share a personalistic and humanistic approach with Bergson. The fundamental difference between their leaders

and the French philosopher is that for Bergson, inner insight remains essentially in the theoretical stage, whereas according to pragmatists, any knowledge is practical in its definition.

Butler sums up the characteristics of the world from the point of view of pragmatists as follows:

(1. The world, whatever it is, is the future. Because pragmatists are more concerned with human societies and assume that society is a current of change, they pay close attention to the future and assume the world to be what it will be.

(2. Human society is also part of nature and like other natural phenomena in evolution and change. "It does not matter whether God or matter is the Creator of the universe," says James. This suggests that the arguments of the proponents of these two views are not convincing; its future effect must be weighed.

(3.2. The current world is changing. There is nothing fixed in the world.

(4.3. The world is insecure or in an unknown state because everything is changing. There is no definite state. In short, the state of the world, especially for complex human beings, is uncertain and associated with feelings of insecurity, and events may go according to human intentions or cause human extinction.

(5.4. The world is imperfect and uncertain. The world is not a machine that is perfect and its state is known in terms of the occurrence of events, but it is growing and expanding and new events occur and new laws are created. Man is a natural phenomenon and his rational powers prepare

him for new creation and change. In short, the world is neither perfect nor closed, and it may get better.

(6.5. The world is many. The world is made up of many worlds.

(7.6. The world has a purpose. Value appears in the course of life. What is is not separate from what should be, and real values are affected by real circumstances.

. The world has no reality beyond experience. What is appears in experience. James justifies religious beliefs on the basis of their effect on one's life, while John Dewey, another prominent philosopher, scientifically examines the origins of such beliefs and discusses changes in nature in nature itself, not outside it. gives

8. Man is also connected to nature or the world. Man, like nature, is in the process of evolution. The basis of human consciousness in the social context (natural state) reveals the direction and psychological phenomena of man during social life.

9. Man is not the doer of things in the world. Man and the environment must be seen in relation to each other. Man is neither compelled nor captive to events and destiny, nor completely free in his activities. Humans and the environment interact. The intellectual aspects of man enable him to guide developments in the scientific and social fields. Man is not a machine and a complete prediction cannot be made.

10. The world does not guarantee progress. The world does not always agree with human desire, but it can be reformed and developed, and

human beings have an important role in this regard. Humans can be somewhat effective in controlling events. The course of events may not be on the path of progress, so man is obliged to try as much as possible to control events.

Areas of pragmatism

On the background and background of functionalist thought and philosophers who had pragmatic ideas or were influenced in some way by the idea of pragmatism, at least in a negative sense, by proposing ideas of perfectionism in knowledge and idealistic views of truth and Knowledge that is typically not the most accessible to such knowledge has led other thinkers to reject such teachings. They concluded: that the only thing that may be applied is the knowledge that is attainable in practice, or that which we apply in our practical experience. Among the Greek philosophers, the views that are very close to the idea of pragmatism are the views of the sophists.

Protagoras says: Truth is that man knows it to be true. In other words, man is the standard of truth and there is no truth independent of man, so one should not seek imaginary truth, and whatever is used in practice is good. The sophists exaggerated in such a way that even in the courts they considered the right as false and the false as right, and used every means to overcome the opponent and considered their words as truth. Socrates and later Plato rebelled against this idea. Plato noted the rejection of Protagoras' theory

(Science is different from emotion, because emotion is always relative, and science would be impossible if we accepted Protagoras' theory.

Moreover, if Protagoras is right when he says that whoever is the judge of all things, then the patient must judge and judge the medicine, not the physician. This (ie, the belief in the existence of facts independent of the mind) is present in all important theories up to Kant. Their real existence and knowledge was certain, and it was Kant who, with his critical question and the Copernican revolution, rejected the hypothesis that he was a man confronted with reality and sought to know it.

In sophistical dialogue and later dialogues, he defined truth as the conformity of thought with reality.

St. Augustine says: Truth is what it is, of course, the truth is revealed as far as it is possible for the knower. Augustine's theory of truth is characterized by the establishment of a relationship between truth and God. Thus Augustine continued the Platonic and Neoplatonic tradition by elevating truth to the supreme realm beyond time, but he brought it closer to the threshold of divinity than he did. In his view, God is pure truth and in him all truths are united. If this world is destroyed, the truth remains, and acknowledging the truth is actually believing in God.

Aquinas, among other medieval philosophers, also acknowledged the existence of reality and the knowledge of truth from it:

For us, a proposition is true when it is in accordance with the objects, but if we mean the objects themselves, then we say that they are true to the

extent that they are in accordance with God's knowledge, so the truth in us is the relation of correspondence and trust with objects. The truth about reality is independent of us. There is a correspondence between the object and what we can call the form of the object in the knowledge of God. And first of all, its status and order are in accordance with God's knowledge. This distinction has become the source of distinction between rational or absolute truth and logical truth or relative and additional truth.

Francis Bacon

With the beginning of the Renaissance and the evolution of the West in the new era, the first thinkers and experts of this movement, namely Francis Bacon and Descartes, were more influential in the new thought than others. Bacon has a special place in this regard, that is, in rejecting idealistic and perfectionist views and opinions about truth. He rejects philosophical ideas from which no benefit can be gained and is the forerunner of pragmatic thought in the new era:

From his student days, Bacon misrecognized the ways and means of his predecessors and contemporaries, and considered them often futile, vague, rhetorical, solid, static, and, in short, fruitless.

Dr. Rowley, his first narrator, says:

(At the same time, a student hated the philosophy of Aristotle and not himself... and became aware of its worthlessness and ineffectiveness, and recognized it as sterile and effective in matters and disputes, but barren and sterile in the production of work for the comfort of human beings.

However, he later decided to create an active and progressive philosophy that would be useful and effective in human life, and decided to come up with a new plan and a new philosophy based on and in line with the natural sciences, and to help human beings know nature and Gaining power to help capture it.

"Bacon's influence on his morals," says Sorley.

(One of the aspects of belief was in the practical result of science, which is of special importance to him, and he considered the first difference between his (new logic) and the old logic in this, and this is the characteristic of the new philosophy.

"Science has no intrinsic value and is a tool for gaining power. Science gives man a kind of power. This science wants to be in accordance with reality," wrote Bacon. I do not want it to be true in my understanding, knowledge for man is like a tooth for a lion, I want to use science in practice.

If a wrong theory benefits me in practice, it is superior to a 100% correct theory that is not useful in practice.

They did not say that action is the criterion of cognition, they said that we have nothing to do with cognition at all. Suppose an intellectual in a backward society comes to rely on his principles and rejects the nationalist, or uses the same idea to save his people, and if this idea has proved successful in practice (he has done a good deed). This is other than to consider action as the criterion of the idea that everything we have

concluded in practice is the truth, and if we do not conclude from something in practice, it is not the truth.

This instrumentalist view of science (ignoring the aspect of achieving the truth that has negative effects and mentioning it) has been positive in another way and has left good effects.

Bacon's method consists of three parts: (observation of nature) (experience) and (title of natural laws), which, unlike Galileo's deductive method, is completely inductive and practical in originality. He claimed that the goal of man in modern science is not only knowledge of nature but also mastery of nature in order to be able to develop the conditions of the environment and human life.

In fact, it was this aspect of giving importance to man in the thinking of Bacon and the pioneers of the Renaissance that led to all these metaphors, discoveries, and scientific advances in post-Renaissance Europe (with all the flaws in Bacon's utopia) Medina has a new ideal and sent a new message to scholars and researchers, sending them to new tasks such as the global cooperation of scientists and scientific institutions. "Practicing the practical sciences and avoiding the purely theoretical sciences has made him aware, and in this way he has made a great contribution to the knowledge of humanity," he says.

"If we succeed in this, we will owe more to Chancellor Bacon," Diderot writes in the introduction to the French Encyclopedia.

Bacon placed great emphasis on the practical application of science and, like (the companions of the originality of action), considered science that was separate from practice to be worthless and invalid. In New Atlantis, the utopia itself, it always speaks of a science that expands the boundaries and realms of man in nature. It shows the longevity and maintenance of the youth forces. It follows that he strongly believes in the mission and practical duty of science, and as Rasi has pointed out:

"Bacon is usually considered to be the first person to say that science is power," says Russell.

In fact, Bacon has said this with a lot of emphasis. The point is that he has emphasized the importance of science with a new emphasis, and Needle Band has also written:

(Bacon is not a goal to know man and nature, but the practical result of that goal.)

According to him, Bari is the goal of the science of action, and science that does not do important work is a colorless and lifeless thing and is not worthy of humanity. Let them rebuild things according to their intentions.

We learn psychology in order to live properly with our fellow human beings, and so we pursue every science for its practical benefit; Because pursuing science apart from the current needs of human beings leads to a school philosophy that is fruitless and a waste of time and a waste of life.

In his articles, he has tried to offer a special practical benefit for the study of any science, even history and poetry, so that it does not seem useless and useless; As he wrote:

(Reading history makes man wise. Poetry gives grace. Mathematics brings thought. Natural sciences make deep and meticulous. Ethics brings dignity. Logic orthodoxy and power argue.

Thanks to the study of human wisdom, he gains the power to correctly understand the differences between things and to split even a single hair. And finally, if human reasoning and explanation is weak, one should study the form of trials.)

It is noteworthy that not only did he not give credit to inactive science, but as if Goethe had ridiculed it to the extent that he wrote:

(Humans should know that only God and angels watch in the play of human life)

It is also worth noting that just as he considers science without action to be worthless, he also considers action that is not based on knowledge and opinion to be worthless, and therefore he looks at both theoretical balance and balance to discover the forms of laws. Practical.

Evaluation of discovery and enlightenment in philosophy is as much the basis of science as it is the basis of action. Bacon, with all the importance he attached to action, was not narrow-minded, unlike some of the companions of the originality of action, and did not look only at the immediate benefits of science, but did not look one-sidedly and believed

that the soul of truth is attractive and the light of knowledge radiates. Which draws the mind to itself and justifies itself in its meaning, so in addition to science which has practical efficiency, there is also radiant knowledge that reveals the facts, natures, and forms of things; facts that are useful in the first place. They do not have a specific;

Imam may later bring benefits that no one thought of in the beginning. (What I am discussing, although actually useless, but actually has many benefits.) Therefore, he criticizes the ancients, especially the teachers, whose wisdom was often fruitless and devoid of practical benefit, both immediate and future benefit. Bacon's thought is fundamentally concerned with action, and recognizes practical results as the surest and highest sign of the validity of philosophies, and places great value on practice; Because they provide the means of human comfort in life, he considers a philosophy that is based on practical results to be worthless and invalid, and in this position he compares philosophy with religion, and thus he thinks that we have been warned in religion: our faith Therefore, philosophy must also be judged by its results, and if it is devoid of practical results, it must be declared vain and invalid. In short, as Clay has noted, the basic premise of Bacon's thought is that (the validity of any philosophy is equal to the production of work and the contribution to the well-being of human beings). At the same time, he believed in practical originality in its conventional sense, that is, one who did not consider practical utility as the criterion of truth and correctness of ideas and affirmations, but considered truths as divine images or designs that are engraved on nature with perfect and beautiful lines. And

he considered truth to be in accordance with reality, but he always considered truth and benefit to be one and the same.) And this direction is a very effective ground in the thinking of pragmatism. Basically, this idea of the commercialization of science is the dominant feature of modern European thought after the Renaissance, while in the past Aristotle said: Ashraf is the science of divine science because it is the least profitable; But today they say: Science must give man power to dominate nature.

(In fact, the history of Western thought has gone through three periods of traditionalism, modernism, and post-modernism. The lowest of it (nature) can not be identified with human intellect. Other great parts of the world can not be identified with human intellect. The solution to all of them is that in the post-modernist period, the idea that reason is incapable of understanding and knowing anything, that we have no way of knowing the world, and that we must be satisfied with the same ghosts and phenomena we receive from the world, gradually spread.

What led to this thought and distrust of human beliefs and perceptions of reality were the thinkers who denied the mirror-like nature of reason. The first was Hume. Hume said that the human intellect could not control its emotions and instincts, and even if it could, it would not be desirable. After him, Kant says: The human intellect is glasses instead of a mirror. The mind is the spectacle of the human soul, and whenever man wants to pay attention to the world, he pays attention with the spectacle of the mind. The point is that there is no way to know if the universe is really what red glasses show, for example, or just a part of the world as my

glasses show it, because we cannot have eye glasses. Take our eyes off us and think without a mind.

Descartes

Whether Descartes can also be called an influential figure in pragmatism, it must be said that Descartes does not exclude material things because he is capable of recognizing man, and this in turn leads to Kant's skepticism and Kant's view of External objects (nouns and objects in themselves are never available) can be influential in the school of pragmatism.

By raising the question of the clarity and distinction of cognition, Descartes in fact sought to escape this crisis of skepticism about the perception of external reality and the perception of the truth of external objects.

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By raising the question of the clarity and distinction of cognition, Descartes in fact sought to escape this crisis of skepticism about the perception of external reality and the perception of the truth of external objects. Because they are open in the way with them. Here it is

appropriate to speak in the language of William James about the roots of the idea of pragmatism in the empirical philosophers of the profession:

Locke and Hume pragmatically critique the spiritual essence. Locke expresses personal identity in terms of its pragmatic value through experience. He says that it means consciousness; that is, the fact that we are in a moment of We remember other moments in life and feel them all as parts of a single personal history, and rationalism explains this practical continuity in our lives with the unity of our carnal essence. س Deprive us. Is our situation a bit better because we have a carnal principle?

According to Locke, our personal identity consists exclusively of characteristics that can be defined pragmatically. That this identity exists in a spiritual principle other than the investigable facts is merely a strange fantasy. But Locke does not passively believe in an essential soul beyond our consciousness.

William James goes on to generalize and express his pragmatic views as follows:

(The general burden where he criticizes matter is absolutely pragmatic. Matter is our same as our feelings of color, hardness, and so on. Emotions are the only meaning of matter. Matter is a name that is equally true of feelings.

Hume also rejected not only matter but also the soul as an independent substance and viewed it functionally.

William James quotes:

Hume and most of the empirical psychologists after him denied the soul except as a name for provable connections in our inner life. Kant is the second philosopher to play a role in postmodern thought and distrust of our beliefs.

Probably no philosopher has been as influential in modern thought as Kant (Kant, who as a teenager was acquainted with the language of the followers of the originality of reason by Leibniz Wolff as a teenager, tried to avoid dealing with the language of the originality of experience in his critical philosophy. These two different currents created a unified language, which later became the father of the languages of educational philosophy and the philosophy of originality.

Regarding Kant's views on the realism of perception and the ability to perceive external affairs, they have written:

(According to Kant, contrary to what has been taken for granted in the theories of the originality of reason, there is no agreement between us and the outside world. Kant does not believe that what is in us is really the second version of the nobility of its objects as they really are and in the soul. According to Kant, there is no realm of independent objective facts to be identified by man, and we cannot perceive the world of objects as they really are and in themselves.

Because if we want to understand it, we have brought it in the forms of our minds. So our theoretical intellect is not able to know the world and what we know is the world of our experience.

In such an idea of the world, which we must always strive for in order to reach its truth, without ever being able to reach it, it seems that the soul and God are also ideas that we cannot prove with theoretical intellect. It is practical intellect and the call of duty that leads us to the principles of the subject matter necessary for the stability of the moral law, that is, to the will, the soul, and God. The problem of identification means that we do not take for granted the possibility of knowing the outside world from the beginning, but examine the possibility of knowing ourselves. It was first theorized and systematically done by Kant.

(The whole evolution of German philosophy after Kant is the consolidation of the power of reason and the attempt to revise Kant's philosophy to prove that we can know metaphysical realities by reason. According to Hegel, reason is essentially the power to perceive and know the whole and wholeness .

That part of Kant's critical philosophy which discusses the possibility of metaphysics and the possibility of knowing the intellect of affairs per se (God, the soul, and the world) is the transcendent debate, and this is where it has influenced pragmatist thought.

(J. S. Pierce [another pragmatist philosopher] rejected the arguments in Kant's analysis but found much valuable in the dialectical debate. He

says: Kant studied the rational forms of God and immortality and free will. And he has accepted them for reasons that are doubtful to the students of the seminaries, but in the eyes of the experimental scientists he is certain.

It is difficult to estimate the extent to which Kant's philosophy of knowledge influenced Pierce, but there is no doubt that Feiminger was influenced by Kant in following the religion of the originality of action in the book (philosophy as it were).

Not only does he acknowledge that he owes much to the transcendental controversy and other parts of Kant's philosophy, but he also tries to show how a particular kind of religion of the originality of action which he believes in has already been foreseen in those discourses. Limiting attention to the positive teachings of controversy and ignoring most of the other claims of Kant's philosophical system leads to originality of action, and limiting attention to the whole teachings of transcendental logic and regardless of Kant's moral works leads to a kind of experimental or non-phenomenal religion.

Kant distinguishes between three aspects of metaphysical issues. Metaphysics as natural desire, metaphysics as science, and metaphysics as critical science.

"Metaphysics is certainly possible as a natural human desire," he says. The reason is that it has existed throughout history; But it is not possible if we look at metaphysics as a science and consider it as the application of

rational concepts in the supersensible, and in the third view it is possible if we look at metaphysics as a critique of this possibility.

Kant believed that it was impossible to understand with rational concepts more than empirical matters.

(Whenever we want to issue judgments about the world of the soul and God that have a theoretical aspect, since they are not given in experience, there is a ruling against them, and in principle, scientific knowledge about those subjects cannot be obtained. He had a theoretical idea.

Kant considers the reason for the failure of theoretical cognition in the propositions of theoretical reason (the existence of God and his absence) to be:

(Discussing these is useless because it is not provable and the only thing that is possible is that these propositions can be accepted in the field of practice in ethics. Because it is not provable because our understanding carries and makes a scientific proposition in Experimental materials are effective.

Kant never doubted the existence of matter and the external world, but adds that we do not know anything for sure about this external world, and only what we know for sure is its existence.

But since the existence of existence, which is one of the categories of understanding, is possible on empirical material, and according to Kant's philosophy one cannot even attribute existence to external things, hence we say that there is in fact no satisfactory enlightenment. ارائه did not

offer knowledge of the outside world, and therefore philosophers after Kant, under the influence of him, sought what works in practice.

Let us return to the controversy over Kant's transcendence. Kant concludes after the premise mentioned: The human intellect can not obtain a theory about the categories: God, the soul and cosmology:

(Any action taken by religion or science in telling final and definite facts and facts will only be considered as hypotheses... and science that wants to go beyond the tangible will be subject to contradictions. To inform... and to remind the divine philosophy that substance, causality, and existence are the ultimate categories; that is, only the aspects and states of the bodily class and the regulation of the senses are applicable only to the appearances and phenomena that enter our minds. It cannot be applied to the affairs of the world (which are only conjectural and inferential)... that is, God cannot prove the survival of the soul by reason.

William James points to Kant's influence on pragmatism. He describes the method of pragmatism as follows:

The pragmatic method is first and foremost a method of resolving metaphysical disputes that might otherwise be endless. The pragmatic approach in such cases is to try to interpret each concept by tracing its practical consequences, and if this or that concept is correct, what is the practical difference?

If no practical difference is found, then the different divisions have practically the same meaning and the dispute is futile. Whenever it is

serious, we must be able to show the practical difference that results from the legitimacy of this or that side of the conflict.

Kant's famous statement (I rejected science to make room for faith) can be understood in this context that Kant thinks that when in the transcendent debate it is impossible to prove or disprove God and religious and metaphysical propositions in Indeed, he closed the way for the unbelievers of God;

Although, according to Kant's principles, the existence of God cannot be proved rationally, the existence of God cannot be denied rationally. On the other hand.

Hegel

In Hegel's influence on pragmatism, the categories of time of honor and dignity can be mentioned:

(Some general theories common in that period that led to the religious elaboration of pragmatism is the notion of the time of the conception of value or dignity. Give more importance to time Hegel created the idea of prioritizing the future in theories of practical goodness, thinking that objects should be considered as they were growing and flourishing, and that the future was an essential aspect of time. Relying on this, the followers of this religion have criticized the conventional belief in the truth and said:

The disadvantage of conventional philosophical systems is that in them, truth as it happened is considered a pre-existing reality and considered to

look to the past, while in the opinion of William James it should be looked to the future; That is, the rightness or wrongness and the rightness and wrongness of thoughts and meanings should not be judged according to the principles that are their source, but should be considered according to the results obtained from them; For example, if we have a true idea of a chair or a door, the truth of these ideas is that we can sit on that chair and close and open this door. Even in matters far removed from practical life, we judge according to their results.

Marx

Other influential thinkers in postmodern thought are the distrust of the beliefs of reason and the role they play in Marx's pragmatism. It does not matter that we receive the reality completely unconsciously distorted, for our own class interests and not of our own free will.

(Marx believes that: ultimately philosophy should be to change the world and believes that real recognition is achieved only in practice. The originality of the tools brings it closer.

(What is of primary importance to human beings is their need to survive and thrive. Human beings need work and production for this purpose. The idea is also involved in this process, but the action comes first and the idea comes second.

In his early writings, Marx used ideology as an idea as opposed to reality as an action. Marx sometimes sees ideology as human consciousness in

all scientific disciplines and sometimes especially social, political and economic ideas.

Niche

In the course of examining the views of leading philosophers in the pragmatist movement, we come to Nietzsche.

Freud and Nietzsche are influential in postmodern thought. Thus: Freud believes that we are aware of a part of our psychic realm.

Freud showed that: Incidentally, our mental realm is wider than our realm of consciousness. For example, the iceberg in the ocean, ten percent of which comes out of the water and the rest is hidden in the water. In fact, many of our positions and assumptions (apparently beliefs) are influenced by our subconscious mind. All our arguments are fabricated. First we take a stand and then we shave the reason for it.

Nietzsche said that man's primary desire is to gain power. What governs all mankind is the will to power. All other desires are manifestations of the power-oriented will, and this power-oriented will includes knowledge.

What we think of as a factual report is a report that empowers us. What proposition humans accept is based on what proposition seeks to empower them and what proposition seeks to weaken them. .

Humans feel power from (man is eternal) and from (man is not eternal) a feeling of weakness. Nietzsche was followed by the Frenchman Foucault. The common denominator of all these thinkers is a kind of distrust of the

fact that we have realistic images of the universe, but each of them has somehow reinforced this distrust.

The combination of these is a kind of suspicion of perceptual powers. That is, it is more realistic to look with suspicion. This suspicion has been a major trend since the 1950s. This current claims that: Reason cannot be considered as a completely reliable source of knowledge. William James also contributed to this idea. He gave a lecture in the United States in 1903 called (The Will to Believe) in which he showed that the beliefs we have are not all due to reasoning. Hope and love or hate and sometimes from the pressure of public opinion and sometimes from personal interests and sometimes it has a logical argument. So only part of our beliefs have a logical argument;

For example, we all say and believe: peace is better than war, it is the best democratic system, there are electrons, but we have no logical argument for them. He also had a kind of suspicion of perceptual powers.

(Nietzsche sees cognition as an instrument and a means to power. Finally, Nietzsche concludes that any identification of man is a permissible form based on the likeness of all beings to man.

Because of these ideas, Nietzsche should be considered one of the pioneers of the school of practical good. He criticizes the notion of truth in various ways and says: the falsity of a verdict is not an objection to that verdict and the authorial verdicts precede the verdicts are false verdicts, but these false verdicts are the most important verdicts for preserving life

(we see Kant's influence on Nietzsche). The other side says: preservation of life is the right and it is something that is accepted by the whole society for the benefit of preserving life.

(Nietzsche says: There is no truth... science does not come to the truth and is not more than a suitable ratio to help preserve and develop and our lives. And it is a constantly moving mistake that never comes close to the truth because there is no truth.

What motivates us is not the will to be truthful. To compete for one's own sexuality and the work of a preacher and even to do good to a benefactor is to neglect others.

(Nietzsche, instead of Kant, who asks: (What can I know firmly and firmly?) Asks (What is good for me to know? What kind of knowledge is possible to advance the will and existence to Help me and what kind of cognition will hurt them?

What am I in? Truth and knowledge are the servants of man, not man the servant of truth. What has absolute status is life, and the existence of those who observe its requirements, not knowledge, and its acquisition, and man builds knowledge, so it is proper for a human being to benefit from one knowledge but not be entitled to another knowledge. Why do some people deserve metaphysical arguments and others do not?

He answers that the will to know must be one with the will to power. There are many things I do not want to know. The limit of knowledge is also determined by wisdom.

Nietzsche, in contrast to scientific objectivity and like Goethe, believes that the quality of one's knowledge depends on the quality of one's moral-existential existence, and this goal is achieved without resorting to religious guarantees. Therefore, knowledge and seeking it are not unconditional and absolute matters. If they help to advance the ideal (life), they are acceptable and approved. If they encroach on its territory, they are condemned and condemned. Life cannot be defined because its definition is equal to this. It will be to follow the intellect that is the servant of life.

Compared to the Greek philosophers, Nietzsche is very close to the sophists who saw man as the standard of truth. He completely rejects the world of Platonic truths:

(Nietzsche considers the world of Platonic truths to be something that comforts the human mind from the lack of truth and stability in the world and the senses; more importantly, it also creates a task. But Nietzsche believes that the world of facts is now an idea which does not work at all and does not even provide a basis for creating a task, a useless and superfluous idea, and therefore let it be rejected and rejected.

The world as Plato saw it superior to the senses of this sensory world is of no use to Nietzsche and must be set aside.

Other pioneers of pragmatism include Ernst Mach and Darwin.

(Ernst Mach, an Austrian, believed that what was economically viable in his mind was true. He writes: The truth is the correspondence of the signs

with itself and with its sequence, and Goethe has said that a fruitful thought is fruitful and whatever he believes is true.

It remains to be seen why the religion of pragmatism took root in this century. Here are the scientific factors and specific conditions of the nineteenth century for the emergence of pragmatism:

The views of three pragmatic philosophers (Pierce James and Dewey)
Pierce

Pierce has something to say about theory (meaning) that can be expressed in one sentence: (what is real is done).

Pierce says:

(The meaning of a concept is related to behavior

Pierce sometimes interprets all metaphysical sentences as positivist. Almost all metaphysical statements are ontological or repetitive; meaning that one word is defined by other words and they are solved by dust. They will be delivered, which can be studied with the help of observational methods of the original sciences, thus pragmatism is a special kind of positivism.

On the meaning of pragmatism for Pierce, William James writes:

(To develop a mental concept, we only need to define how that concept is used to create a behavior, and that behavior is meaningful to the melancholy.

We examine the theory (meaning) in Pierce's view:

The main task of thought is to provide the methods and characteristics of action

It is therefore unreasonable to say that thought, regardless of its relation to its sole function (function), is meaningful. The way of expressing those beliefs or in relation to feelings and emotions that they have towards a particular expression.

(From the point of view of the history of pragmatism, Pierce's major contribution is his analysis of meaning, that is, his formulation to clarify concepts, and if we consider in general terms this effort of his, what is the useful motive for making our objective content Give our concepts and do not let the (vague) words take the place of clear thoughts.

William James

William James articulated the philosophy of the American people. He measured truth by the measure of action: (What is done is true.) James did not consider the questions of the scientific community, but the questions that were in the minds of most people.

Among American philosophers, the works of no philosopher other than Wolf Waldamersen

The extent of his work was not well received. William James is a second-rate philosopher and first-rate psychologist. James was a firm believer in observation and experience. Argument and reasoning that is not based on observations and experiences were considered useless:

(Pragmatism می turns its back on verbal solutions for fixed a priori reasons on fixed principles on systems dependent on the so-called absolutes and origins.

William James believes the truth:

To judge an idea, one must look at its practical consequences. From his point of view, (right) (good) and (useful) are mixed. Right thought has good and useful results, and wrong thought has bad results. In other words. An idea that has good and beneficial results is right and an idea that has bad and harmful results is wrong.

He writes about views that are correct but purely theoretical

(Assuming it is a correct idea or belief, what is the distinct difference between its correctness in personal practical life?] Misconceptions are those that we can not do it's because of events that become real..... the greater the difference between pragmatists and non-pragmatists in the sense of the word truth. When pragmatists speak the truth, they mean exclusively something about imagination; That is, they work, while anti-pragmatists mean the objects themselves when they speak the truth.

In such a case, views are the only tools:

(Theories become tools, not answers to riddles that soothe us; any notion that moves us from one part of our experience to another and saves work is just as true.

(If one thinks whether stealing is the right way to solve his financial problems, according to the test of practical authenticity, it can be said that: Accurate evaluation of the possible consequences of stealing leads a person to the conclusion that stealing is right).)

What is the use of mere philosophical arguments from which no conclusion can be drawn:

(If we assume that it is the end of the world, what is the use of arguing that man is compelled or free to do evil, or good, or even about the existence or non-existence of God?)

In short, in comparing Pierce and James, both Pierce and William James left meaning and truth to achievement and to the future; But the results and achievements that James sought in meaning were more of a personal return than a social one. Your future will emerge.

(Pierce said that what is real is done, and James said: What is done is real. Pierce went to the lab to find out the truth, and James was led to practical life.)

William James actually believed in things that did not appear to be based on his empirical foundations:

He has gathered his firm belief that in observing science and discovering truths one should only resort to observation and experience with the clergy and the interest in religion. And the companions of the sense

protest that it pays attention to the issues of the first philosophy and esoteric affairs.

(Lately, researchers have become more and more convinced that it is either not possible for us to determine substance, celibacy, and soul survival at all, or if it is, our knowledge today is not enough to achieve that goal, and it is better to know how spiritual effects and Let's study the soul and in these studies, let us go to the method of new sciences, that is, observation and experience.

As today, psychology is one of the most important and remarkable techniques and has been the center of philosophy, while it is considered as a natural science and the sciences, and it also mediates the transfer from nature to theology, as was the case with William James. Is.)

There seems to be a psychological aspect to why William James dealt with matters of religion and tried to harmonize them with his philosophy:

William James's father had a deep religious feeling and his guilt in the psychological conflict between the scientific conception of the world which was interpreted as a mechanistic conception and denied human free will and the religious conception which included belief in God and human free will. Found.

Hence James addressed religious issues and interpreted it with pragmatism:

(A pragmatic analysis of religious beliefs reveals that the question of whether or not to accept religious beliefs should be returned to which way of thinking is better and more effective in practice. تو اند can find that some beliefs are beneficial and effective for some people; that is, a certain set of beliefs, when accepted, provides a more satisfying life.

(Belief in God gives man strength and meaning in life. He experienced this especially in the crisis he faced in his youth.

Relying on the free will of faith in God, as well as phrases from the Bible that helped him overcome the crisis and move from death to life.

James actually believes:

Although the idea of God is not as clear as the mathematical ideas, but in the sense that it establishes an ideal order and belief in it causes people to consider painful matters as temporary and partial, and the hesitation and separation as absolute and final. Do not assume that it has practical value in human life and leads one to peace of mind, so God is justifiable.

William James believes in a third kind of perception for religious experience and paints it scientifically; That is, along with sensory perception (external) and esoteric perception (internal), the third type is called religious perception.

(James considers them to exist through works obtained from religious experience of the supernatural. An area other than the perceptible world must be real because it has works of its own in this world. It is religious experiences that connect with the spiritual world.

John Dewey

(William James, on the other hand, is concerned with solving some of the individual questions about John Dewey's theory of belief in the broader social problems that the United States faces in its rapid development in this century.

They have written about the importance of John Dewey in contemporary American philosophy:

(Perhaps the most influential and influential American thinker in recent times is Dewey. And to use the leadership of human intellectual activities in relation to contemporary social issues

Whitehead says about the role of Dewey:

(We live in the middle of a period under the influence of John Dewey

Dewey's interpretation of the philosophy of pragmatism is represented as follows: Dewey pursued the originality of religion in such a way that man is inherently a creature facing problems and problems that must be resolved, and thought is a means of resolving problems with Easy to operate. Our situation creates problems and the mind seeks to solve them.

Dewey philosophy is also called naturalism

According to Dewey, this religion considers the intellect as a convergent intellect to experience and enables man to solve his problems with the means of intellect and science, and considers the evolution to be accompanied by some artistic, spiritual and moral successes. Therefore,

naturalism in this Religion is more common. Dewey strives to apply the method of experience to all sciences:

Dewey posed the question of what has led to this astonishing situation in scientific work (the last three centuries in Europe) and these excellent and strange results. Can such a thing be applied with similar success to other human fields, and in They used?

He writes about the method of his predecessors in science and philosophy:

If Aristotelian logic worked in its time, today we need a coherent theory of research that can be used in other fields (a valid model of empirical and scientific research in science). This does not mean that all fields of research should be Physical sciences to be delivered.

According to Dewey, philosophy is a science that helps us solve the problems of worldly life:

What is needed these days is the modernization of philosophy in the light of the problems we now face. Which helps in the development of new useful technologies in the effort and conflict with the environment and in building a better world in which some of the issues and problems that we now face and gradually need to be resolved.

The goal is not to study the knowledge of the world, but to gain control over the environment by those who must spend their lives in it.

Methodology

The school of originality of action is empiricist in which the role of sense and experience in establishing a secular culture is obvious.

According to pragmatists, senses are acquired and the result of objective conditions. According to Dewey, the meaning of an object depends on the effect it leaves, and the idea of good or bad depends on the activities it triggers in the organism, the result of which is satisfactory or unacceptable. In addition to the result, the origin of the theorem is related to what has taken place in society. Therefore, the truth depends on the actions of human beings. In symbolic interaction, as in pragmatism, formal logic has a vague basis, and reason never has a valid and comprehensible position.

The difference between behavior and action

Sociologists such as Talc Parsons and Scheller, and activists such as Herbert Blummer, focus on the complex meaning of action (or action) rather than on behavior. By preferring the term action, Sheldon refers to behavior as a set of observable movements as well as the individual manner of observable movements. Action in human activity implies something that connects the agent with his environment.

The four distinguishing elements of action and behavior are:

1- The goal that the agent has in mind during his action;

2- Agent position;

3- The senses of the agent who guides his behavior;

4. His effort, that is, the force he uses to maintain balance and change the environment to adapt to external factors.

If we receive these four components in behavior, it can be called action; But if the first and third factors are considered, action can be called a behavior that is determined by the intervention of the agent's conscience as a specific type (action) of a general gender (behavior).

Aspects of pragmatism from a philosophical standpoint

1. In their view, truth or reality does not exist readily in the real world, but is activated as we function in the world.

2- People's knowledge about the world is based on its usefulness, which undergoes changes as soon as it becomes inefficient.

Individuals also define their social and physical cognitions based on their usefulness.

3- Knowing the actors depends on their practical work in the world.

Examining the characteristics of the school

According to the principles of pragmatism, action is the most important benefit of anything; So the most important achievement, in addition to the benefit, is in terms of the spread of new humanism in the West, and especially in the United States. Undoubtedly, the new humanism has emerged from the context of pragmatism.

To examine this school, its features can be summarized in several cases:

1- The problem of body - mind; Pragmatists did not distinguish between body and mind; Because they considered the distinction irrational; Those whose critique of these two issues turned into a philosophical battle. They saw differentiation as the result of artificial segregation and separate categorization for easy analysis. According to them, what is known as the psyche is the result of the physical actions of the senses;

The mental and non-psychological states that act in order to place the action in a sub-state rely on an imaginary distinction, and the solution is to try to be based on human action, not the product of body or mind.

2- Individual and society; They did not separate the individual and society from each other and thought that individuals are formed in society and by society, but at the same time the creative man makes individual and social action as it is. When there is unity between society and individuals, their social reactions are modified and the issue becomes

what effect each individual has left on society and what effect it has received from it.

3- Rejection of metaphysics; This arises from the indistinguishability of mind and body, as well as the individual and society, in the thoughts of pragmatists. From their point of view, the achievement of the mind appears in the body and the senses; Because they are the basis of action. Also, when the individual and society are considered together as a unit, the issue of socio-human action also changes.

Thus, the school of originality of action, along with schools such as positivism, originality of existence, etc., formed the basis of Western culture and, despite all differences, were effective in denying religion and promoting secular culture and opposed the rule of church and religion; Both those who considered religion to be imaginary and superstitious, and those who sought to reform religion.

General characteristics of pragmatism

Philosophy in this school is devoid of theoretical goals and pays more attention to practice.

The philosophy of pragmatism is basically English and American, and in France Bergson and Lorraine, and in Italy the Provincines and Papinians are the pragmatists.

Pragmatism, though most prevalent in the United States and the United Kingdom, is not limited to it. It gained a large following around 1900, especially in Germany. Karl Marx, Lenin, Georg Simmel, and

Hansfeyminger also demonstrated to the empiricist systems, and the positivist approach is generally related to it.

According to the owners of this philosophy, the purpose of life is the action, not the opinion, and consequently the activity of the intellect is first and foremost in the source of the practical effect, and the intellect's job is to help life and facilitate livelihood and satisfy our various desires. Therefore, science has practical value and validity, and the job of science is not to acquaint us with the nature of objects, but to give them the means to influence and possess them and to make them compatible with our needs. Thus truth in this philosophy is conceived in a way that is contrary to what conventional philosophers thought about it.

Sometimes twentieth-century schools of thought reacted to past philosophies by reacting against any kind of rationalism.

The philosopher is the best guide, but not in abstract concepts but in living effort and decision... Pragmatists based their work on life and action.

Sometimes to the originality of life, which has centered life and considered it something unique and broader than thought. Sometimes to pragmatism and sometimes to instrumentalism of practical utility even in logic and truth.

In fact, pragmatism is a perverse form of pragmatism; That is to say, instead of knowing the truth, he considers the forms of action and experience as the principle and the opinion as the means: all these

pragmatists consider thought as a function of thought, action as a function of action, and attack rationalism.

In

their empiricist approach, they base their views not on pre-experiential concepts but on living experience, rejecting both idealistic and mechanistic conceptions of the world as abstract and rationalist conceptions that define evolving and dynamic reality. Nature is known as the flow of constant being. Natural science is an important and fundamental part of biology.

The picture that the pragmatists present of the world also seems to be separate from other philosophies; Because when we pay attention to what is shown in experience instead of generalities, it leads to a cosmology separate from other philosophies.

Materialists, idealists, and others present an image of the world that always has certain attributes. Contrary to this view, pragmatists face a pluralistic world; A world with many attributes and possibilities that cannot be studied all at once, but the world must be studied experimentally as it appears and evolves. As nature progresses, our understanding of it must evolve.

In fact, it is a kind of lowering of philosophy and insights into the practical life of philosophizing:

According to the theory of the originality of practical goodness (pragmatism), the purpose of our rational activities is to try to solve the problems that arise during our efforts to examine experience. "We think

only to solve our problems," says James, one of the leading philosophers of pragmatism. For example, the idea that our world is a spiritual world.

In American-British pragmatism, it is not just a theory of cognition; often a whole philosophy of life is added, which is very similar to Bergson's philosophy.

According to that, reality is not a fixed thing, but it is freely creative and in flux. Understanding is incapable of receiving it. Every knowledge is based on experience. Anglo-American pragmatists also share a personalistic and humanistic approach with Bergson. The fundamental difference between their leaders and the French philosopher is that for Bergson insight remains essentially at the theoretical stage, whereas according to pragmatists, any knowledge has a practical aspect by definition.

Characteristics of the world from the point of view of pragmatists

Butler sums up the characteristics of the world from the point of view of pragmatists as follows:

Whatever the world is, it is the future. Because pragmatists are more concerned with human communities and think of society as a process of evolution, they pay close attention to the future and think of the world as what it will be. Human society is also part of nature and like other natural phenomena in evolution and change. "It does not matter whether God or matter is the Creator of the universe," says James. This suggests that the

arguments of the proponents of these two views are not convincing and its future effect should be weighed.

۲. The world is changing. There is no fixed thing in the world.

3. The world is insecure or in an unknown state because everything is changing. There is no definite state. In short, the state of the world, especially for complex human beings, is uncertain and associated with feelings of insecurity, and events may go according to human intentions or cause human extinction.

4. The world is imperfect and uncertain. The world is not a machine that is perfect and its situation is known in terms of the occurrence of events, but it is growing and expanding and new events occur and new laws are created. Man is a natural phenomenon and his intellectual powers prepare him to create new things and guide change. In short, the world is neither perfect nor closed, and it may get better.

5. The world is many. The world is made up of many worlds.

. The world has a purpose. Value appears in the course of life. What is is not what it should be, and real values are affected by real circumstances.

7. The world has no reality beyond experience. What is appears in experience. James justifies religious beliefs on the basis of their impact on one's life, while another prominent philosopher, John Dewey, scientifically examines the pragmatism of the origin of such beliefs and discusses changes in nature in nature itself and not outside it.

8. Man is also connected to nature or the world. Man, like nature, is in the process of evolution. The basis of human consciousness in the social

context (natural state) reveals the direction and psychological phenomena of man during social life.

9. Man is not the doer of things in the world. Man and the environment must be seen in relation to each other. Man is neither compelled nor captive to events and destiny, nor completely free in his activities. Humans and the environment affect each other. The intellectual aspects of man enable him to guide developments in the scientific and social fields. Man is not a machine and a complete prediction cannot be made.

10. The world does not guarantee progress. The world does not always agree with human desire, but it can be reformed and developed, and human beings have an important role in this regard. Humans can be somewhat effective in controlling events. The course of events may not be on the path of progress, so man is obliged to try as much as possible to control events.

Factors in the onset of pragmatism

It remains to be seen why the religion of pragmatism took root in this century. Here are the scientific factors and specific conditions of the nineteenth century for the emergence of pragmatism: for it may have been the state of information derived from biology and psychology, as well as the state of religious beliefs and critique of science in that period. According to Darwinian biology at the time, it was known that there was a struggle for life, and that parts of living things remained in evolution,

which was beneficial to this struggle. These considerations are not far from nature if the mind tends to equate truth and usefulness.

On the other hand, it was clear in psychology that what is in the human mind is directed towards a purpose. "All carnal things have an end, and the mind is always on the move," says William James. At the same time, the elaboration of non-Euclidean geometry and the idea that of all possible geometries it is easy to think, which makes one of them the preferred one in the study of nature, and is generally important in the theory of Poincaré and II. Also the theory of issuance and wave...

From psychological and social aspects, the grounds for pragmatism can be examined. In fact, the emergence of pragmatism in the nineteenth century also had psychological and social contexts that influenced it:

American-rooted movement pragmatism has profoundly influenced intellectual life in America and is gaining influence in Britain. It was a show. The expedient found that their methods and theories could be useful in solving intellectual problems and advancing human progress. Therefore, from the theory of practical goodness through theoretical thinking, it shows the way to get rid of a lost person in the desert. (We will say) that this is the criterion for determining the value of the truth of theories that have been considered as the criterion of science. Thoughts are like tools to solve problems and solve the problems that human beings face. goes.

And, in principle, philosophy is taken less seriously in the United States than anywhere else because of its ambiguity and complexity, and because it is far from direct interests.

And the emergence of philosophy in the form of the school of originality makes practical nature and pragmatism more natural.

The profitability of new science

Here it is examined that the new science is a profiteering and profiteering science. Francis Bacon, the father of new science and philosophy, should be considered as the driving force behind this business:

From the very beginning, philosophers of the new age, such as Bacon, interpreted science not only as a means of discovering truth and satisfying human curiosity, but also as a useful means of satisfying human needs and providing new techniques and new forms of human practical power. Which later proves its error and inaccuracy, like Ptolemy's hypothesis in astronomy was useful for man of that time.

That's enough to make it true. Dr. Davari writes about the transformation of Westerners' attitudes toward science from the satisfaction of curiosity and science for knowledge (Aristotle's thought) to science for worldly gain in the new age:

In the past, Aristotle used to say: Ashraf is the science of divine knowledge because it is the least profitable; But today it is said that science must empower man to dominate nature. (But it is necessary to know what is meant by useful science and what is the best and most

useful benefit.) Medicine is a useful science and everyone knows its benefits, but the benefits of medicine outweigh what everyone knows. Great physicians have not even practiced medicine for the benefits we know. Hippocrates' oath is related to medical science;

But Pasteur in his research had no consideration other than science. He was not in the grip of profit and loss at all and did not care about everyday affairs at all. He was a lover of science. Philosophy is also a lover of science and supports science (as Descartes considered philosophy the root of science). They ask, they do not seek knowledge. Of course, science is beneficial science, but what is benefit? ... Today, the new science is not a science to be conquered, but to be conquered itself, and it has abandoned the philosophy that was its root.

Aristotle considered the first philosophy to be the most noble science, and one of the criteria for the honor of science was that it was useless. This means that the more noble the subject of science, the more noble that science is, and because the subject of the first absolute philosophy exists.

Metaphysics is useless, but it is not really useless in the true sense of the word. Science that brings man closer to perfection cannot be called useless. The benefit of science is not only the benefit of the trading market.... No one denies the value of new sciences; science is disgusting; That is, what is the perfection of science to consider a new form of science, which is only to occupy the world? If man's attachment to the world increases every day and they do not allow him to be reminded of his captivity in pride, have they not hindered his true progress? New

science and technique is not an issue if it is a tool, but new science is today's equipment that we have no choice from.

Basically, a science that is related to power by will and its chance is to enable human beings to occupy the world and man in the direction that the essence of the new technique requires, how can it free man from the shackles of falsehood and his belonging to the right? ... The debate is about what relation man has with science and how his truth is realized in this relation? این In this new world, everything either comes out of power and leads to power or is negligible. Islam with a science that gives man pride and power (of course, power here means power that brings pride and with that power we want to trample on the weak, as in Nietzsche's theory, which considers morality to be weak and believes in the superman) But power that is compatible with morality and forgiveness is also praiseworthy.

Of course, if the bond of science is broken by pride, it is desirable and sometimes even obligatory to pay attention to it.

One should not assume that a person's motives in the field of his scientific thought have any effect:

The lustful and predatory nature always tries to use science (which leads man to perfection) as a tool in the service of its lusts.

In this case, a science that seeks profit and a science that does not seek to understand the truth but strives for power, his destiny falls into the hands of human desires. In fact, the profitability of new

science is one side of it, and in fact it is based on what benefits me;

That is, humanism:

(Methodology teaches that no science other than the new science is valid and invites them to come to this science solely and exclusively and consider it an absolute science (and this is other than the invitation to learn)...

Some people in the world of fantasy and desire say: Science should serve the peace and happiness of human beings; But peace and justice will not be established until the foundations of the current world of oppression are broken. Some may shrug their shoulders and say that science is science دیگر but in the words of Maulana Jalaluddin Rumi we also have (the science of the manger)... Descartes said: (I will not accept anything unless its proof is obvious to me.) It is about humanism and the new relationship that exists between man and existence. In this regard, man not only attributes science to himself, but also becomes the criterion for the correctness of scientific rules and even the end of study and research in it, and this knowledge is beneficial science... .

So are all the people of this age at a loss? The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him) meant what is beneficial for the health of the human soul and heart and brings them closer to the truth; But in our time, profit and loss are in the longing of the world, and the criterion and amount of it is the statistics itself, which takes the form of reason and makes it reasonable and logical. The benefit of science from the point of view of Islam, according to the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allaah be upon him), is the etiquette of the clergy, and the benefit of

knowledge from the point of view of new science makes one more dependent on the material and worldly worlds.

A review of the critique of pragmatism

One of the issues and perhaps the most central issue of pragmatism is the issue of truth and its meaning and the criterion of being real. What makes Pragmatism stand out is the issue that needs to be addressed.

(The ancients considered the truth to be in accordance with reality and the essence of the matter.

For example, it is not current in mathematics or it is current in experience.

Today, the definition itself is controversial and rejected, and for example, pragmatists and positivists do not accept it. And pragmatists say:

Truth is that which is useful. One of the reasons for the rejection of this old definition by modern Western scholars is that:

1. This definition does not apply to mathematics because mathematics does not really apply.
2. This definition does not apply to historical theorems either, because historical reality has been destroyed.
3. Some have said: We cannot speak of truth in empirical matters either. These forms are not in reality in the mind itself.
4. The question of the evolution of science has also cast doubt on this criterion. We see that a scientific theory is correct at one time and is considered incorrect at a later time. Therefore, the pragmatists said: that theory was useful in its time and this one is useful in this time.

The reason why a number of people today have changed the definition of truth in the eyes of their predecessors is the same example of the fact that truth has changed from the meaning of truth (according to reality) to efficiency in practice. If we take these new definitions of truth seriously, the result is, is it true at all?

Here we give a brief overview of the views that in the West lead to doubt in the ability to understand the truth, and then examine whether it can be said that there is a truth or not.

(Some scientists believe that the power of human intellectual judgment is only in the (phenomena), ie the appearances of nature and determining their relationships that can be experienced, and research on mites and supernatural beings, both natural and supernatural, is beyond the reach of human intellectual judgment. .

1. Hussion believe: There is nothing in the intellect except what is sensed, and philosophy, because its problems are beyond the bounds of the appearances of nature, is beyond the bounds of human study (only the natural sciences are real). Kant believed in it and believed in it. According to Auguste Kent, in the third period of mankind, he does not study phenomena with real and rational causes, but only determines the relations of tangible objects. The essence of reason believes that it denies philosophy.

The deniers of philosophy argue against the rejection of philosophy in two ways in order to deny the ability of the intellect to perceive truth:

1. Through psychology: It means that the basic materials and elements of the human mind are not sufficient to solve those problems because the basic elements of the human mind are limited to the forms of sense and the intellect can do nothing but possess those forms of sense.

2. In a logical way: any theory and hypothesis that is not tested in practice is not reliable and the issues of rational philosophy can not be tested in practice; Because, for example, one cannot test whether existence is original or nature?

Doubt in the ability of the intellect to understand the truth leads to doubt in other perceptions, including doubt in sensory perception; Therefore, it is debatable here that:

(Is there a truth in principle? Of course, everyone agrees. Even skepticism, even error. Cognitions must be examined, and the means of knowing cognition is the logic of something.

3. Is the truth temporary or permanent? Researchers used to believe that the truths are permanent. : The ancients because they did not pay attention to the principle of change in nature...

Therefore, according to the principle of change in nature, it must be said: truths are temporary, not permanent. They have not realized that even reality itself is in a temporary place (matter) and in a permanent place (flow حرکت). But is conformity to reality temporary or permanent? The answer is that it is not temporary, because if we consider the changing reality at a particular time, knowledge of it is permanent; For example,

Sassanid history (to which science does not change even though it was a variable reality) because what is bound to time is an external reality, not our knowledge of it or our knowledge of mathematics and physics. They said of permanence:

So a mental concept is either not true at all and is a lie, or if it is true it is always true and in accordance with reality.

But there are three points:

1. This is the permanence of the truth about the real sciences, such as the philosophy of mathematics, and credit sciences, such as the social and political sciences, do not have such a condition.
2. The issue of permanence and temporality of facts is related to certain facts, not probable facts. Experimental sciences are dependent on past experiences and will be invalidated if new experiences reject them. Therefore, they are temporary.
3. The criterion of collective agreement for the truth and other criteria can be temporary.

In the new logic, the criterion of cognition has changed and the criterion of action is:

Criteria for recognition; That is, for what reason and from where is one thing true and right knowledge and one thing wrong. The criterion of cognition In Aristotelian logic (analogy) self-knowledge means that in order to know that cognition is a real cognition, we want a reason and that

reason also requires a reason, and so on until we reach a cognition that is the criterion itself and that is obvious. So self-knowledge is the criterion of cognition.

Since the time of Francis Bacon, a new logic has emerged and says: (as opposed to Aristotle's logic) The criterion of correct cognition (to some extent it is cognition, however) is ultimately action.

Therefore, the difference between Aristotelian logic (analogy) and the new logic is not in the lack of importance of the old logic to experience and the importance of the new logic in experience, as we have said, it is in the criterion of cognition. Although Aristotle valued experience very much. They have said since Bacon: We have no theoretical and obvious knowledge. All cognitions are theoretical and unknown, and the only way to know right from wrong is through action. Therefore, the action found extraordinary value in terms of being a standard. But how did this come about?

They said: For the correctness of a theory and thought, first it is induction and by observing a theory it comes to our mind, then we try that theory in practice, and if in practice the opposite does not work, we accept it, and if in practice, we accept his exam well.

Like ways to get rid of traffic. The problem with this theory was its religious beliefs. That God exists is a soul... With this new criterion we cannot measure its correctness, so we deny it; But they can be accepted

by the old standard; Because in the end we prove it with reasons to reach the obvious.

Some people in the West were more fair and said: the only criterion is to know the action, but where we have religious knowledge چون because we can not understand in practice is right or wrong (we do not know) but those people said it is a lie because It is not proven in practice and examination.)

In fact, there are two rights and benefits:

(Our ancient scholars used to distinguish between right and benefit and said: to be right means to be in accordance with reality - in essence - is one thing, and benefit and benefit is another. Now whether these two are related or not is another matter. It is a wrong idea, but the same wrong idea is good for human beings; for example, an old sick father has a young son who has gone abroad to study. But it is not true. The man cursed the king.

If the king heard that the verdict of his murder was certain, the king asked his minister what he had said.

Paul Folkier criticizes pragmatism as follows:

(The best change of truth is in discovering human potential abilities and making them real.

1. In this theory, truth is defined only by the words (success) and (useful), which are vaguely expressed; What is successful and desirable is the

desires of a bandit for one thing and desirable for another benevolent, but there is no answer as to which category of desires can be considered true.

A sentence before it is investigated or corrected is either true or false. For example, it is raining now in Beijing. It is either true or false before it is investigated.

3. The theory of practical goodness is self-defeating because the promise that every truth is useful requires that at least one proposition be absolutely true, and the promise that there is no theoretical and general truth, and that all truths are scientific and personal. He himself has accepted a theorem that has become a theoretical and general truth

If the criterion of being true is usefulness, we have in fact believed in something irrational because:

If we want to see the idea of usefulness and the idea of result, we see what this usefulness is and what the results are. Therefore, as Aristotle said, one must stop somewhere: a theory in which the source of truth and results is considered to be good is destructive, because these results must also be known. And he knew that these results are good and he also knew what the word good means, and thus the verdict on the results in three ways includes the notion of truth and the definition of truth to it is contrary to logic.

Bradley also criticizes the originality of the action:

Even if we accept Hume's statement in reason that he is nothing more than a servant of desires, religion is the originality of science; Because

one of the deepest desires of civilized man is a sense of curiosity and the desire to achieve truth with its own intention.

Regarding pragmatism about truth, Master Motahhari examines the issue from the point of view of whether we consider action as the criterion of truth or the key to truth.

(The fact that action is the key to thought is the right word, but it does not mean that the key is unique in that it means this (that action is the standard of thought everywhere)...

Some believe that the measure of right and wrong of human thought is only action; For example, they say: When you say that someone considered his friend a good person, after traveling with him, his opinion changed and he said that he was a bad person, except that experience and action proved to him. So it is by action that man can test his thought whether it is right or not.

But many things cannot be tested while they are the truth and clearer to man than any truth; For example, far is impossible... These are pure science and cannot be experienced. Marxism places great emphasis on practice. Islam does not consider practice as the only criterion for the correctness of thought.

Is action the key to cognition? Yes. Action means feeling means induction and observation is the introduction and the initial stage of cognition, then the mind must think and reason, and if we give an

example, the building whose first key is action and its rooms have other keys. Here, too, there are different ways of knowing.

Major drawbacks to the logic of action:

a. Assuming the standard of action (for the truth) is correct, it can not always be used. It is impossible to realize that it is impossible at all and it is just a theory.

B. Practical logic accepts at least one self-standard and self-evident cognition. . In other words, (action is the criterion of cognition) is self-evident and cognition is the criterion itself.

J. In this statement: (is the criterion of action) is itself part of Aristotelian logic. Russell says: (If cognition is correct, it results in action) is correct, but it cannot be said: (If cognition is correct in practice, cognition is correct) because it is true that (if this object is a walnut, it is round) but it is false (if This object is round).

Russell says: Whatever came to the conclusion in practice is not correct, like Ptolemy's hypothesis, which worked in practice but was not correct, so it should not be said: (The hypothesis is correct because it worked in practice). Perhaps there are other theories among It should not be raised and in practice it should give results where it is not known. Whether we consider the earth to be the center and the sun to revolve around it, or vice versa, we can predict an eclipse. Another example was medicine based on the four elements and the four natures (moisture, constipation, heat and cold) and diseases were cured. Even in some diseases, such as diphtheria,

the old treatment is better, so it is not that if a hypothesis works in practice, but if the hypothesis is correct, it works in practice, but it is not common.

۲. This statement (action is the criterion of thought) must be based on its originality

We measure actions by action, which is not the case, and therefore it is rejected.

In the continuation of this discussion, Master Motahari states the criterion of action for the truth according to the Qur'an and Nahj al-Balaghah:

There is a verse in Surah Ra'd which states: Whatever is true is also useful. It rains and floods flow, and the foam on the water flows accordingly, but this is the water that stays and sinks to the ground, and the foam of the water disappears, and falsehood does not remain, and what is useful is the truth. Is as lasting as water remains on earth.

The answer of pragmatists to the problem that if the criterion of truth is action, the thief also considers his work right because it is useful for him: (In addition to direct results, the last effects should also be considered).

The irony is that theft, although directly beneficial to the thief, is detrimental to society. Critics respond: How long do we have to wait to see its achievements?

Other forms of pragmatists: what works; What does it mean? for me? For the community? For humanity? We need a moral plan to say whether a

belief is good or bad. It works is ambiguous. Pragmatism: Well it is what works.

Other drawbacks: If the property of recognition is the satisfaction of people, some may enjoy the idea that the moon is made of cheese, but this is not true.

However, critics and critics believe that the originality of action makes human issues, reactions, and feelings, which lie more in how we perceive different ideas, positive ideas with their own dignity and credibility, and in response to pragmatists, no There is no criterion other than benefiting man.

Result:

Finally, it should be noted that the positive aspects of pragmatism should also be mentioned; What is undeniable is that in the philosophies of life and practice there are appropriate propositions that bring us from the throne to the carpet, make us aware of empirical facts, and speak of the effectiveness of theory. Pragmatists, I mean those who have such an approach, or at least some of the key aspects of such an approach, see themselves as agents in the world, not observers. This means that they are not passive beings who receive only impressions, but are organisms that interact with their environment. They are more inclined to have an organ that does things in their physical or social environment, and sometimes they are creatures that are affected by the environment, and also, at times, appear to be active in both aspects. Unlike early empiricists as well as

twentieth-century analytic philosophers, pragmatists do not limit experience to sensory experience; they consider the experience of pleasure or suffering, anger or fear, effort, and the like. In addition, as James often points out, we also experience relationships. But the latter case is not my focus in this article.

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